

1 Dppa4 is likely functional during TE lineage commitment in the human embryo.

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here discovery of Dppa4
9 as a lineage commitment factor in embryonic stem cells of the human embryo.

10 Citations

11 1. Eckersley-Maslin, M., Alda-Catalinas, C., Blotenburg, M., Kreibich, E., Krueger, C. and Reik, W.,
12 2019. Dppa2 and Dppa4 directly regulate the Dux-driven zygotic transcriptional program. Genes &
13 development, 33(3-4), pp.194-208.

14 2. De Iaco, A., Coudray, A., Duc, J. and Trono, D., 2019. DPPA2 and DPPA4 are necessary to
15 establish a 2C-like state in mouse embryonic stem cells. The EMBO Reports, 20(5), p.EMBR201847382.